

FLUOBERYLLATES

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From conductometric measurements it has been shown that four fluoberyllate ions namely, $[\text{BeF}_3]^-$, $[\text{BeF}_4]^{2-}$, $[\text{BeF}_5]^{3-}$ and $[\text{BeF}_6]^{4-}$ exist in solution.

A search in the old literature for the double fluorides of beryllium reveals the existence of the salts of the type, MF, BeF'' ; $2\text{MF}, \text{BeF}_3$, where M stands for K, Na or NH_4 . That beryllium in case of the latter compound ($2\text{MF}, \text{BeF}_3$) is the constituent of a complex fluoberyllate ion $[\text{BeF}_4]^-$ and that this complex ion shows close analogy with sulphate ion have been well established by Sarkar and Ray (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 987).

The isolation of $\text{NH}_4\text{F}, \text{BeF}_2$, the salt of type MF, BeF_2 , from phase rule study is of very recent origin (Novosselova and Averkova, *J. Gen. Chem. U. S. S. R.*, 1939, 9, 1064). Beryllium shows certain characteristic analogy with aluminium in the periodic table. The formation of beryllates and the role of BeCl_2 , similar to that of AlCl_3 in organic reactions, will serve as typical examples (Bredereck *et al.* (*Ber.*, 1939, 72B, 1414; *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1939, 52, 445). In case of aluminium, three double fluorides viz., $\text{NH}_4\text{F}, \text{AlF}_3$; $2\text{NH}_4\text{F}, \text{AlF}_2$; $3\text{NH}_4\text{F}, \text{AlF}_2$ have been isolated from phase rule study (Novosselova, *J. Gen. Chem. U. S. S. R.*, 1940, 10, 1547). From the facts stated above, the question naturally arises that in addition to $[\text{BeF}_3]^-$ and $[\text{BeF}_4]^-$ other complex fluoberyllates, analogous in composition to those of complex aluminium fluorides may also exist. Studies of such higher complex fluoberyllates in solution by physico-chemical measurements form the subject matter of the present investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ammonium fluoberyllate was prepared by digesting beryllium hydroxide in requisite amount of ammonium bifluoride and crystallising the product. The crystals were collected, dissolved in warm water and recrystallised. The crystals were washed twice with ice-cold water and finally with alcohol and dried in air. A stock solution was prepared and its strength determined by estimating beryllium and ammonia. The complex was decomposed by concentrated H_2SO_4 in a platinum basin and beryllium precipitated as hydroxide and ignited to BeO . Ammonia

was estimated by distillation with alkali and absorbing the distillate in a standard acid and titrating back the excess acid.

Beryllium fluoride was prepared by heating ammonium fluoberyllate in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide in a crucible furnace at 300°, and finally at 400° for about an hour. A stock solution of the substance was prepared.

Beryllium was estimated as BeO in the same way as was done in the case of the previous compound. For the estimation of F' a known volume of the solution was evaporated to dryness with excess Na₂CO₃ and the temperature was slowly raised till the mix melted and it was kept at fused state at high temperature for some time. The melt was cooled and extracted with water and filtered. In the filtrate fluoride was estimated as lead chlorofluoride. The ratio of Be to F' was found to be 1 : 1.970.

Beryllium sulphate (BeSO₄, 4H₂O) was prepared by digesting Kahlbaum's beryllium carbonate in H₂SO₄ and crystallising the product. The crystals were dissolved in warm water, the solution acidified with sulphuric acid and recrystallised. The crystals were washed three times with ice-cold water and finally with alcohol till free from acid. A stock solution was prepared and its concentration checked by estimation of Be as BeSO₄.

Ammonium Fluoride.—The stock solution was prepared with Merck's NH₄F of reagent quality. The strength of the solution was ascertained by estimating both ammonia and fluorine in the same way as was done in previous cases.

The conductivity apparatus was fitted with amplifying system so that experimental error in determining resistance did not exceed 0.1%. The measurements were made in an electrically regulated thermostat by which the temperature could be kept constant within ± 0.05°.

In these observations the reciprocals of the observed resistances were sufficient to draw the curve showing divergence from the additivity rule. So the cell constant was not determined. The thermometric titrations were conducted in the same way as were done in a previous communication (Purkayastha and Sen-Sarma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 32). The conductivity cell except the the platinum plates were coated with paraffin.

Conductometric and thermometric measurements have been made with BeSO₄, BeF₂, and (NH₄)₂ BeF₄ with NH₄F in each case. The breaks in the curve indicate the composition of the solution at which complex formations take place.

TABLE I
Conductance measurements with BeSO₄ and NH₄F
 Temp. = 30.0°.

1		2	3		4	5	6		7	8
<i>M</i> /20 - Be SO ₄ soln. in c. c.	Water added in c. c.	Conductance of (1) × 10 ³ = C ₁ .	<i>M</i> /20 - NH ₄ F soln. added. in c. c.	Water added in c. c.	Conductance of (8) × 10 ³ = C ₈ .	C ₁ + C ₈ = C ₅ .	<i>M</i> /20 - Be SO ₄ soln. in c. c.	<i>M</i> /20 - NH ₄ F soln. in c. c.	Conductance of (6) × 10 ³ = C ₆ .	C ₅ - C ₆ .
50	50	12.81	50	50	13.49	26.30	50	50	20.25	6.08
45	55	11.98	55	45	14.75	26.71	45	55	19.77	6.94
40	60	10.90	60	40	15.89	26.84	40	60	19.52	7.32
35	65	9.896	65	35	17.19	27.088	35	65	18.98	8.128
33.35	66.65	9.596	66.65	33.35	17.53	27.126	33.65	66.65	18.75	8.376
30	70	8.812	70	30	18.25	27.082	30	70	19.05	8.012
27	73	8.187	73	27	18.96	27.157	27	73	19.40	7.757
25	75	7.733	75	25	19.81	27.543	25	75	18.63	7.913
23	77	7.227	77	23	20.00	27.227	23	77	20.00	7.227
21	79	6.774	79	21	20.41	27.184	21	79	20.44	6.744
20	80	6.538	80	20	20.73	27.266	20	80	20.81	6.656
18	82	6.094	82	18	21.15	27.244	18	82	21.25	5.994
15	85	5.289	85	15	21.85	27.089	15	85	21.92	5.169
14.3	85.7	5.101	85.7	14.3	22.15	27.254	14.3	85.7	22.11	5.144
12	88	4.448	88	12	22.64	27.089	12	88	22.63	4.458
10	90	3.850	90	10	23.03	26.880	10	90	23.03	3.850
5	95	2.271	95	5	24.53	26.801	5	95	24.67	2.131

Difference from the least divergence from the additivity rule in each case has been plotted against composition (Fig. 1, curve I).

TABLE II

Thermometric titration of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{BeF}_4$ with NH_4F .

$M/2$ $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{BeF}_4$ soln. (48 c.c.) was taken in the flask and $3M$ - NH_4F soln. added from the burette by 2 c.c. at a time.

NH_4F added.	Thermo. readings.	$3 \times 10 \times$ diff. from orig. readings.	NH_4F added.	Thermo. readings.	$3 \times 10 \times$ diff. from orig. readings.	NH_4F added.	Thermo. readings.	$3 \times 10 \times$ diff. from orig. readings.
0 c.c.	2.300	0.000	12 c.c.	2.178	3.660	22 c.c.	2.128	5.160
2	2.270	0.900	14	2.108	3.960	24	2.120	5.400
4	2.240	1.800	16	2.155	4.350	26	2.112	5.640
6	2.230	2.400	18	2.143	4.710	28	2.104	5.880
8	2.200	3.000	20	2.137	4.890	30	2.099	6.030
10	2.189	3.810				32	2.093	6.210

$3 \times 10 \times$ difference from the original thermometer readings in each case has been plotted against the c.c. of ammonium fluoride added (Fig. 2, Curve II).

TABLE III

Thermometric titration of BeF_2 with NH_4F .

$M/2$ - BeF_2 soln. (48 c.c.) taken in the flask and $4M$ - NH_4F soln. added from the burette by 2 c.c. at a time.

NH_4F added.	Thermo. readings.	$\frac{1}{2} \times 10 \times$ diff. from org. reading.	NH_4F added.	Thermo. readings.	$\frac{1}{2} \times 10$ diff. from org. reading.	NH_4F added.	Thermo. readings.	$\frac{1}{2} \times 10$ diff. from org. reading.
0 c.c.	2.335	0.000	12 c.c.	2.268	2.845	26 c.c.	2.022	4.005
2	2.727	0.540	14	2.210	3.125	28	2.000	4.176
4	2.630	1.075	16	2.165	3.350	30	1.980	4.275
6	2.520	1.575	18	2.130	3.525	32	1.962	4.385
8	2.430	2.025	20	2.100	3.675	34	1.946	4.445
10	2.342	2.465	22	2.070	3.825	36	1.928	4.530
			24	2.048	3.935			

$\frac{1}{2} \times 10 \times$ difference from the original thermometer readings in each case has been plotted against the c.c. of ammonium fluoride added (Fig. 2, Curve III).

TABLE IV

*Conductometric titration of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{BeF}_4$ with NH_4F .*Temp. -30.0° .

$M/20$ - $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{BeF}_4$ solution (60 c.c.) was taken in the cell and $3M$ - NH_4F solution added from a micro-burette.

NH_4F added.	Resistance.	$\frac{1}{2} \times$ diff. from final resistance.	NH_4F added.	Resistance.	$\frac{1}{2} \times$ diff. from final resistance.
0.03 c.c.	22.57 ohms	0.530	1.75 c.c.	12.57 ohms	1.530
0.25	20.13	5.305	2.00	11.93	1.310
0.50	18.25	4.370	2.25	11.39	0.9400
0.75	16.66	3.575	2.50	10.92	0.7050
1.00	15.45	2.970	2.75	10.39	0.4400
1.25	14.39	2.410	3.00	9.919	0.2045
1.50	13.53	2.010	3.25	9.510	0.0000

$\frac{1}{2} \times$ difference from the final resistance has been plotted against mols. of ammonium fluoride added (Fig. 3, Curve IV).

DISCUSSION

The curve I (Table I) showing divergence from the additivity rule in the conductometric measurements of BeSO_4 with NH_4F has four clear maxima. The compositions of the solutions at these maxima indicate respectively

FIG. 1.

the formations of $[\text{BeF}_2]$, $[\text{BeF}_3]'$, $[\text{BeF}_4]'$ and $[\text{BeF}_6]'''$ in solution. There is a flattened portion of the curve lying in between the maxima due to the formation of $[\text{BeF}_4]'$ and $[\text{BeF}_5]''$. The flattened nature at this region of the curve is an indirect evidence for the formation of $[\text{BeF}_5]''$ in solution.

The curve III (Table III) due to the thermometric titrations of BeF_2 with NH_4F has also four breaks which indicate the presence of $[\text{BeF}_3]'$, $[\text{BeF}_4]''$, $[\text{BeF}_5]''$ and $[\text{BeF}_6]'''$ in solution as in the previous case.

The curves II and IV (Figs. 2 and 3) respectively due to thermometric and conductometric measurements of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{BeF}_4$ with NH_4F show two clear breaks in each case. These breaks must be due to the

formation of $[\text{BeF}_5]''$ and $[\text{BeF}_6]'''$ in solution.

These conclusions have been drawn from two independent physical methods, which differ from each other in fundamental principle, one depending upon the colligative property of the solution and the other upon the temperature change serving as an index to chemical reactions.

Evidences derived from both the methods indicate that there exist four complex fluoberyllates, namely $M[\text{BeF}_3]'$, $M_2[\text{BeF}_4]'$, $M_3[\text{BeF}_5]''$ and $M_4[\text{BeF}_6]'''$ where M stands for a monovalent cation.

From the evidences set forth above the previous idea that there is one single fluoberyllate $[\text{BeF}_4]'$ or there are at least two ($[\text{BeF}_3]'$ and $[\text{BeF}_4]''$) is no longer tenable. Further, these evidences not only expand the idea as regards the number of fluoberyllates existing in solution and not only serve as instances for analogy of beryllium to aluminium but also establish the hexa co-ordination of beryllium in solution. Beryllium in consideration of its position in the periodic table with respect

to boron, aluminium and magnesium is expected to exhibit co-ordination number higher than four.

FIG. 2.

Curve II—48 c.c. of $M/2 \cdot (NH_4)_2 BeF_4$ solution was taken in the flask and $3M-NH_4F$ solution added from the burette.

FIG. 3.

Curve IV— $M/30 \cdot (NH_4)_2 BeF_4$ soln. taken in the cell and $3M-NH_4F$ added.

Curve III—48 c.c. of $M/2 BeF_2$ soln. taken in the flask and $4M-NH_4F$ soln. added.

A phase rule study with ammonium fluoberyllate and ammonium fluoride is in progress.

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